

Influence of the heat-treated microstructure of additively manufactured Ti-6Al-4V on the fatigue behaviour

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Abstract: Successful orthopaedic implant systems must restore the physical function of the affected joint or bone and promote bone regeneration. They must therefore have properties that come as close as possible to natural bone, i.e., have adapted mechanical and biological behaviour. In addition to maintaining the physical functions, the patient-specific customisation of implants is playing an increasingly important role. Additive manufacturing processes offer an excellent starting point for this due to their high degree of design freedom. The following abstract deals with the influence of heat treatment on the additive manufactured microstructure of a Ti based alloy and the resulting change in dynamic fatigue behaviour.

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I. Introduction

Implants designed for long-term use in the human body, such as joint replacements, are subject to a complex and constantly changing spectrum of stresses (see figure 1). On one hand, this includes static and particularly dynamic stresses resulting from natural movement patterns and everyday physical activities. On the other hand, these implants are also exposed to (electro-)chemical influences caused by the multifaceted environmental conditions in the body, such as changes in pH levels and aggressive body fluids [1].

Figure 1: Acting loads on an implanted prosthesis

Clinical studies indicate that one of the primary risk factors for the occurrence of infections in humans after implantation is the implant itself and its interactions with the surrounding tissue [2]. To better adapt load-bearing medical implants to the individual needs of patients in the future, several different approaches are being explored. One possible option to improve the product behavior in contact with the tissue is to functionalize and redesign the surface. For this purpose, additively manufactured open-

porous Ti-6Al-4V hybrid structures are used, which are functionalised by integrating antibacterial and bioactive agents.

In the following, the influence of the dynamic load and the associated microstructural fatigue in various states will be analysed and evaluated.

II. Material and methods

The hybrid structures utilized in this investigation were fabricated from the advanced titanium alloy Ti-6Al-4V grade 23, employing state-of-the-art additive manufacturing methodologies. The powder bed-based process of selective laser melting (SLM), renowned for its exceptional design freedom, facilitates the production of intricate matrix structures with unprecedented complexity. Specimen fabrication was executed in a Concept Laser Mlab system under rigorously controlled argon atmospherics to ensure optimal process conditions.

These meticulously engineered structures were conceptualized to simultaneously promote osteogenesis and maintain structural integrity in high-stress regions. The hybrid architectures comprise a sophisticated connection of body-centered cubic, periodically repeating, unit cells with a solid material component, as illustrated in figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic model of the specimens consisting of bulk (grey) and body-centered cubic unit cells, BCC (blue) for dynamic testing

Samples were ultrasonically cleaned with ethanol to remove particles after SLM processing. Rapid cooling in laser-based additive manufacturing causes martensitic transformation. This as-built state is compared with a heat-treated state, achieved by heating samples at 800°C for two hours in argon, followed by subsequent furnace cooling.

Samples are metallographically prepared on the bulk side to create a defect-free contact surface for dynamic testing. A servo-electric device conducts dynamic tests in the pressure threshold range at a constant 2 Hz frequency.

III. Results and discussion

The following section presents and discusses the results achieved so far in the field of metallography and dynamic tests. As the tests on the heat-treated samples have not yet been completed, only the current status is presented here.

III.I. Metallographic results

Metallographic analyses reveal clear microstructural differences between the as-built state and the heat-treated Ti-6Al-4V samples (see figure 3). The as-built samples have an acicular martensitic microstructure (α' -phase) whose direction of growth is aligned with the build-up direction of the samples along the z-axis.

Figure 3 Metallographic images of the additive-manufactured alloy Ti-6Al-4V in the as-built state (top) and after heat treatment (bottom)

The rapid solidification of micro-melts and high quenching rates prevent equilibrium microstructure development. This process can lead to concentration shifts in the ternary system. The heat treatment induces a transformation of the α' -phase into the $\alpha+\beta$ -phases [3]. The phase transformation is accompanied by a reduction in the process-induced

residual stresses, which is expected to increase the fatigue resistance.

III.II. Dynamic results

The dynamic tests on the heat-treated samples currently show a tendency to double the fatigue strength compared to the untreated as-built samples. The fatigue strength of the heat-treated specimens is now approximately 0.2 mm (see figure 4).

Figure 4 Wöhler curve for as-built (green) and heat-treated (orange) samples displacement-controlled at $f=2$ Hz

IV. Conclusions

Compared to the as-built state, the martensitic needles turn into a lamellar microstructure due to the heat treatment carried out at 800°C in an argon atmosphere. Initial dynamic tests on samples in the heat-treated state indicate a fatigue strength of the BCC structured samples (see figure 2) of around 0.2 mm for the path-controlled tests. It is therefore clear that a doubling of the fatigue strength can be achieved by subsequent heat treatment and the associated changes in microstructure.

Investigations on the residual stress state of as-built specimens show high residual shear stresses in the martensitic state, which are reduced by the energy input during the dynamic test. These results indicate relaxation processes in the microstructure. According to these investigations, the initial residual stresses should be lower in the heat-treated state. This hypothesis is to be tested in order to confirm the relationships between the microstructure and the dynamic fatigue behaviour of additively manufactured Ti-based alloys.

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